

**Naturally occurring eugenyl acetate as biobased plasticizer for sustainable
polylactide formulations with improved toughness**

D. Barrera-Juca^a, C. Lazaro-Hdez^a, J. Gomez-Caturla^a,
R. Balart^{a,*}, N. Guijarro^b, X. Maset^{b,c}

^a Instituto Universitario de Investigación de Tecnología de Materiales (IUITM),
Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Plaza Ferrándiz y Carbonell 1, 03801,
Alcoy, Alicante, Spain. D.B-J.: dbarjuc@epsa.upv.es; R.B.: rbalart@mcm.upv.es;

C.L-H.: carlaher@epsa.upv.es; J.G-C.: jaugoca@epsa.upv.es

^b Instituto de Electroquímica, Universidad de Alicante, Apdo. 99, E-03080 Alicante,
Spain. N.G.: nestor.guijarro@ua.es

^c Instituto de Síntesis Orgánica (ISO), Universidad de Alicante, Apdo. 99, E-03080
Alicante, Spain.

X.M.: xavier.maset@ua.es

***Corresponding author:** R. Balart - rbalart@mcm.upv.es

*** Corresponding author.**

R. Balart - rbalart@mcm.upv.es

Instituto Universitario de Investigación de Tecnología de Materiales (IUITM)

Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV)

Plaza Ferrándiz y Carbonell 1, 03801, Alcoy, Alicante, Spain.

Tel.: +34 96 652 84 00

Abstract.

In this study, we explore the potential of eugenyl acetate (EAc), a naturally occurring ester of eugenol present in cloves, cinnamon, pepper, oregano, among others, as a biobased plasticizer to overcome the intrinsic brittleness of polylactide (PLA). A theoretical assessment of the miscibility between PLA and EAc is carried out through determination of solubility parameters (δ), and the interaction parameter (χ) of the Flory-Huggins theory. Our findings demonstrate that EAc, with an ester group, an aromatic ring, and a short hydrocarbon chain, shows exceptional miscibility with PLA, as confirmed by their solubility parameters (EAc-19.83 MPa^{1/2}, and PLA-20.66 MPa^{1/2}) and an interaction parameter of $\chi = 0.39$. The incorporation of EAc significantly improves the ductility of PLA, with elongation at break increasing dramatically to 427.7% at 20 wt.% EAc, compared to a brittle 10.2% for neat PLA. However, lower EAc concentrations (5-10 wt.%) do not enhance toughness but instead decrease stress at break. The plasticizing effect of EAc also leads to a considerable reduction in the glass transition temperature of PLA, from 60.4 °C to 35.7 °C at 20 wt.% EAc. Scanning electron microscopy reveals no phase separation and the development of plastic deformation in PLA formulations with 15-20 wt.% EAc. Additionally, all plasticized formulations exhibit full biodegradation in controlled compost conditions in less than 8 weeks. These results contribute to advancing PLA-based formulations that are both high-performance and eco-friendly, supporting the broader goals of sustainable development in polymer science.

Keywords: Poly(lactide); sustainability; biobased; plasticizer; eugenol ester; toughness; thermal properties.

1. Introduction.

In recent decades, there has been increasing interest in the development and applications of biopolymers [1]. Among the wide variety of biopolymers, those coming from renewable resources, and biodegradable have gained special relevance [2-4]. This group includes polymers derived from polysaccharides such as cellulose, chitin, pectin, starch, among others [5-7], as well as polymers derived from proteins such as gluten, casein, soy protein, bean protein [8-10]. Bacterial polyesters or polyhydroxyalkanoates also stand out, among which polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) and poly(hydroxybutyrate-*co*-valerate) (PHBV) have gained increasing relevance [11, 12]. However, polylactide or polylactic acid (PLA) is undoubtedly one of the biopolymers with the greatest industrial presence in sectors such as biomedicine, controlled drug delivery, textile products, automotive sector, 3D printing, among others [13-17]. PLA is usually obtained through a ring-opening polymerization process (ROP) from lactide, derived from the fermentation of starch-rich compounds [18]. Although it has become widely used industrially, PLA is a brittle polymer, with an elongation or strain at break of around 10% or less [19-21]. This leads to low toughness, which limits its extension to various sectors where flexible and ductile materials are required, such as the packaging sector.

It is possible to minimize these limitations through the use of copolymers [22, 23], but this is a high cost and low availability option at industrial level. Physical blending can also minimize the effects of PLA brittleness by developing binary and ternary blends [24-26]. However, in many of the blends, miscibility problems arise between the components [27, 28]. Plasticization is undoubtedly one of the most interesting approaches for improving PLA ductility [29]. Plasticizers reduce the T_g of PLA to values close to room temperature enhancing chain mobility. A wide variety of plasticizers have been proposed for PLA. Among monomeric plasticizers, esters such as citrates [30], cinnamates [31],

tartrates [32], terpenoids [33], and vegetable oils [34], offer excellent plasticizing properties. On the other hand, oligomeric/polymeric plasticizers provide lower migration but usually, miscibility is, in many cases, limited. It is worthy to note the use of oligomers of lactic acid (OLA) [35], as well as polyglycols such as polyethyleneglycol (PEG), or polypropyleneglycol (PPG), and their copolymers [36].

Recently, eugenol has arisen as a relevant building block for the polymer industry [37]. Eugenol is a naturally occurring phenolic compound found in several aromatic plants, especially cloves (*Syzygium aromaticum*), cinnamon, pepper, oregano, among others [38, 39]. It can also be obtained from lignin by a depolymerization process [40]. Its main uses are due to its antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and aromatic properties, which make it valuable in pharmaceuticals [41, 42], cosmetics and personal care products [43], food and beverages [44], and pest control [45]. The increasing interest on eugenol relies on its chemical structure which contains an aromatic ring, a hydroxyl, a methoxy, and an allyl group [46, 47], all of them with a wide range of possibilities of chemical reactions such as epoxidation, hydroxylation, hydrosilylation, hydrogenation (typical of the allylic group), allylation, O-glycidylation, alkoxylation, esterification (typical of the phenol group), O-demethylation (methoxy group), and nitration or oxidative coupling (aromatic ring) [39]. Despite most of the literature related to the use of eugenol derivatives is mainly focused on epoxy thermosetting and vitrimers [48-50], it has also been described its use in polyurethanes [51, 52]. Xuan *et al.* [53], have reported the exceptional plasticization efficiency of eugenyl levulinate and eugenyl valerate on PLA corroborated by a noticeable decrease in T_g of PLA from 59 °C to 16 °C with 30 wt.% of eugenyl valerate processed by the solvent cast method. With the sake of searching for new cost-effective and commercially available plasticizers for PLA, eugenyl esters seem to be good candidates. Bocqué *et al.* [54], have analyzed a wide variety of industrial

plasticizers, and have concluded the optimum molecular architecture of a plasticizer must offer. In particular, they pay special attention to the presence of an aromatic group that provides polarity, an ester group that provide compatibility, and an alkyl chain that provides flexibility by increasing the free volume. Eugenyl acetate (EAc) is the ester of eugenol and acetic acid. As eugenol, it is a phenylpropanoid and it is the second in abundance in many extracts of clove, just after eugenol. It finds similar applications to those of eugenol [55-57]. Moreover, eugenyl acetate is widely available at commercial scale, and possesses all features desirable for an organic compound to be an efficient plasticizer as described by by Bocqué *et al.* In this work, we propose, for the first time, a new application of eugenyl acetate as a double-green plasticizer for sustainable PLA formulations. The novelty of this work relies on the use of conventional extrusion and injection molding processing techniques, which are typically used at industrial scale. The effect of varying the amount of eugenyl acetate on mechanical, thermal, thermomechanical, morphological, as well as its influence on the biodegradation rate is addressed in this work. Also, a theoretical assessment of PLA and eugenyl acetate is carried out by determining their solubility parameters (δ) and its contributions, and the interaction parameter (χ) of the Flory-Huggins lattices theory.

2. Experimental.

2.1. Materials.

The base polymer used in this work was a polylactide - PLA commercial grade PURAPOL L130 with a L-lactic isomer content above 99%, supplied by Total Corbion PLA (Gorinchem, The Netherlands). Its melt flow index (MFI) is 16 g/10 min (ISO 1133-A 210 °C/2.16 kg), and its density is 1.024 g/cm³. Eugenyl acetate (purity > 98%) was supplied by Sigma Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). It is a pale yellow to clear liquid to solid with

a density of 1.079 g/cm³ at 25 °C, a melting point comprised between 24 – 27 °C (at 760 mmHg), and a boiling point of 281 – 285 °C at 760 mmHg. It is soluble in alcohol, essential oils and paraffin oil, while its solubility in water is limited to 98.28 mg/L at 25 °C.

2.2. Plasticization of PLA with eugenyl acetate.

PLA pellets were dried at 40 °C for 1 day to remove residual moisture and prevent PLA from degradation since aliphatic polyesters are very sensitive to moisture. PLA was plasticized with different eugenyl acetate (EAc) weight percentages, ranging from 0 to 20 wt.%. The coding of the different formulations is PLA for unplasticized neat PLA, and PLA/XEAc where “X” indicates the nominal wt.% of eugenyl acetate. The formulations were compounded in a DSM Xplore MC 15 twin-screw micro compounder from Xplore Instruments BV (Sittard, The Netherlands) at a screw rotating speed of 100 rpm. The mixing process was carried out at a temperature of 180 °C for 2 min. After this, the melt was transferred to a micro injection moulding unit DSM IM12 from Xplore Instruments BV (Sittard, The Netherlands), to obtain standardized specimens for further characterization. The injection moulding process was carried out at a temperature of 190 °C using a close pressure of 8 bar.

2.3. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) characterization.

The chemical structure of neat PLA and its plasticized formulations with varying eugenyl acetate content was analyzed using a Bruker S.A. Vector 22 FTIR spectrometer (Madrid, Spain), equipped with a PIKE MIRacle™ single reflection diamond attenuated total reflectance (ATR) accessory (Madison, Wisconsin, USA). FTIR spectra were

collected in the 4000 – 600 cm⁻¹ range with a total averaged scans of 20 with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

2.4. Thermal and thermomechanical characterization.

The effect of varying eugenyl acetate content on thermal properties of plasticized PLA formulations was followed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) in a Discovery DSC25 calorimeter from TA Instruments (New Castle, Delaware, USA) in nitrogen atmosphere with a constant gas flow of 66 mL/min. Samples with average weight comprised between 7 – 10 mg were placed in standard Al crucibles and subjected to a dynamic thermal program consisting on three steps: a first heating from 30 °C to 180 °C was followed by a cooling down to 0 °C and, finally, a second heating step was scheduled from 0 °C to 220 °C. All three steps were carried out at a heating/cooling rate of 10 °C/min. The thermal degradation at moderate-to-high temperatures was followed by thermogravimetry (TGA) analysis in a TG-DSC2 thermobalance from Mettler Toledo (Columbus, Ohio, USA). Samples with an average weight around 10 mg were subjected to a temperature sweep from 30 °C to 700 °C at a constant heating rate of 10 °C/min in air atmosphere. The degree of crystallinity was calculated from DSC data following **Equation 1**.

$$\chi_c (\%) = \frac{\Delta H_m - \Delta H_c}{\Delta H_m^0} \frac{1}{(1 - w)} \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

where ΔH_m stands for the melt peak enthalpy, ΔH_c represents the crystallization enthalpy (which includes both the cold crystallization, ΔH_{cc} , and the pre-melting crystallization, ΔH_{pm}). ΔH_m^0 is the theoretical melting enthalpy of a 100% crystalline PLA, 93.7 J/g [58], and finally, w stands for the weight percentage of EAc.

The dynamic-mechanical thermal properties, namely the storage modulus (E'), the loss modulus (E''), and the damping factor ($\tan \delta$), were obtained by dynamic-mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) in a Mettler-Toledo DMA1 (Columbus, Ohio, USA) on rectangular samples with dimensions $25 \times 10 \times 4$ mm³ working on single cantilever, at a frequency of 1 Hz, and a maximum amplitude of 10 μ m in the free cantilever. A temperature sweep from -50 °C to 100 °C was programmed at a heating rate of 2 °C/min.

Dimensional change with temperature was studied by thermomechanical analysis (TMA) in a Q400 thermoanalyzer from TA Instruments (New Castle, Delaware, USA). Samples with dimensions $10 \times 10 \times 4$ mm³ underwent a dynamic heating program from -50 °C to 120 °C at 2 °C/min, with an applied force of 0.02 N. The coefficient of linear thermal expansion (CLTE) was determined as the slope in the selected linear regions.

2.5. Mechanical characterization.

Mechanical properties were obtained through tensile, Charpy's impact, and Shore D hardness tests. Tensile tests were carried out at room temperature in a universal test machine ELIB 30 from SAE Ibertest (Madrid, Spain) using a load cell of 5 kN, and a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min, as indicated by ISO 527. At least five different specimens for each PLA-based formulation were tested, and the values of the percentage elongation at break (ϵ_B), and the tensile strength or stress at break (σ_B) were averaged. Regarding the impact strength, this was obtained in a Charpy's impact pendulum (6 J) from Metrotec S.A. (San Sebastián, Spain), on notched samples ("V"-type with a radius of 0.5 mm) following the guidelines of ISO 179. The impact strength at room temperature (a_{cA+23}) was calculated as the average of the absorbed energy per unit area of five different specimens. The effect of eugenyl acetate on hardness was evaluated in a 676-D durometer

from J. Bot Instruments (Barcelona, Spain) following ISO 868:2003. The Shore D hardness values were obtained as the average of, at least, five different measurements.

2.6. Surface morphology.

To study the surface morphology, fractured samples from impact tests were first subjected to a sputtering process with a gold-palladium alloy in a Quorum Technologies, Ltd. (East Sussex, UK) sputter-coater. Subsequently they were observed in a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM) Zeiss Ultra 55 from Oxford Instruments (Abingdon, United Kingdom) operated at 2 kV and a working distance of 4 mm.

2.7. Disintegration in controlled compost soil.

The effect of varying eugenyl acetate content on disintegration in controlled compost soil of plasticized PLA formulations was studied. Rectangular samples sizing $10 \times 10 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ were cut, dried at $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 day, weighed, and then buried in a bioreactor measuring $30 \times 20 \times 10 \text{ cm}^3$ with synthetic soil as described in ISO 20200. In these conditions, specimens underwent aerobic degradation at an incubation temperature of $58 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in an air-circulating oven for 8 weeks. For easy removal, specimens were placed in a textile mesh, thus allowing a direct contact with the compost soil. At periodic intervals of 1 week, specimens were extracted from the reactor, then rinsed with water, and finally, reweighed to follow the disintegration process. After this measure, the specimens were returned to the textile mesh to continue with the disintegration.

2.8 Other characterization techniques.

The crystallinity developed by PLA and its plasticized formulations with EAc just after manufacturing, was characterized by X-ray diffraction spectroscopy (XRD). X-ray

diffraction patterns were collected using a KRISTALLOFLEX K 760-80F X-ray generator at 40 kV and 40 mA. The radiation from the CuK α target was nickel filtered ($\lambda = 0.154$ nm). The span of the scattering angles (2θ) ranged from 5° to 70° with a step size of 0.05° and a speed rate of $1^\circ/\text{min}$. XRD were carried out on samples sizing $10 \times 10 \times 2$ mm³.

Moreover, the water uptake of PLA and its plasticized formulations with EAc was studied on samples with dimensions $80 \times 10 \times 4$ mm³. Specimens were immersed in distilled water at room temperature and were taken out and weighed weekly using an analytical balance, for a total period of 13 weeks.

3. Results and discussion.

3.1. Plasticization of PLA with eugenyl acetate.

Figure 1 gathers a comparative plot of the FTIR spectra of neat PLA and its plasticized formulations with increasing eugenyl acetate content. Neat PLA shows the characteristic peaks at 1750 cm^{-1} , and 1182 cm^{-1} which correspond to the stretching vibration of the -C=O , and -C-O of the ester groups. The -CH_3 group shows a characteristic peak at 1452 cm^{-1} which is assigned to its asymmetric bending vibration, and a peak located in the $1380 - 1360\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is attributed to its symmetric bending. The peak located at 1181 cm^{-1} is caused by the symmetric stretching vibration of the -C-O , while the peak at 1080 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C-O-C asymmetric stretching vibration [59]. It can also be seen a small peak at 868 cm^{-1} , that is assigned to the crystalline regions of PLA. As the eugenyl acetate content increases, some characteristic peaks of EAc can be seen in plasticized PLA formulations. Obviously, it shows a characteristic peak at 1741 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to carboxyl of the ester groups [60]. Regarding to the aromatic ring, a peak located at 1508 cm^{-1} is attributed to the C=C stretching vibration, as well as

the peak at 1604 cm^{-1} . A key fingerprint peak for 1,2,4- substitution can be seen at 818 cm^{-1} , and 909 cm^{-1} , which is assigned to C–H out-of-plane bending vibrations [61].

Figure 1. FTIR spectra of PLA and plasticized PLA with varying eugenyl acetate (EAc) content in the spectral region comprised between $2100 - 700\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

As it is provided in Supplementary Information (**Table SI.1**), the solubility parameters of both PLA ($20.66\text{ MPa}^{1/2}$) and EAc ($19.83\text{ MPa}^{1/2}$) are very similar, which leads to a RED value of $0.79 < 1$, thus suggesting good miscibility of EAc in the PLA polymeric matrix. Recently, Patel *et al.* [62], have experimentally determined the Hansen solubility parameters of different aliphatic polyesters, including various PLA commercial grades and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), with solubility parameters in the $20.0 - 21.9\text{ MPa}^{1/2}$ range for PLA, and $19.7 - 20.7\text{ MPa}^{1/2}$ for PHAs. They also have reported exceptional plasticization properties with a lignin-derived plasticizer with RED values < 0.4 with regard to PLA and PHAs, while plasticizer saturation has been observed with

bis(2-ethylhexyl) adipate plasticizer with a RED value of 0.7, thus confirming the lower the RED value, the higher affinity between the polymer and the plasticizer. Gomez-Caturla *et al.* [63, 64], have reported RED values ranging from 0.73 to 0.85 of different terpenoid esters with exceptional plasticization efficiency on PLA. The miscibility can also be assessed through the interaction parameter χ described in the Flory-Huggins lattice theory which is related with the energetic interactions between a polymer and a solvent (or plasticizer). It plays a critical role in predicting the thermodynamics of polymer mixtures and phase behaviour of the system. The interaction parameter, χ includes an entropic and an enthalpic contribution (**Equation 2**). This parameter has been widely used to assess the miscibility between a polymer and a solvent (or plasticizer) [65].

$$\chi = \chi_S + \chi_H \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

$$\chi_H = \frac{v_1}{RT} (\delta_{\text{PLA}} - \delta_{\text{EAc}})^2 \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

The entropic contribution is a constant in the 0.3 – 0.4, but usually, it is assumed to be 0.34 for non-polar systems [66]. Regarding the enthalpic contribution it can be obtained as shown in **Equation 3**, where v_1 represents the molar volume of the solvent (plasticizer), δ_{PLA} , and δ_{EAc} , stand for the solubility parameters of PLA and EAc, obtained by the group contribution method as shown in **Table SII**. If $\chi = 0.5$, it is the so-called θ solvent condition and means the polymer-plasticizer interactions are equivalent to polymer-polymer interactions, and plasticizer-plasticizer interactions. $\chi > 0.5$ means phase separation could occur depending on the system and concentration, while $\chi < 0.5$

indicates good miscibility [67]. The χ interaction parameter has been calculated as indicated in **Equation 4**, considering the entropic and the enthalpic contributions with $R = 8.314 \text{ J/mol K}$, and $T = 298 \text{ K}$, and was found to be $\chi = 0.39$, which confirms good miscibility between PLA and EAc plasticizer from a thermodynamic point of view and suggests no phase separation should be obtained.

$$\chi = 0.34 + \frac{v_1}{RT} (\delta_{\text{PLA}} - \delta_{\text{EAc}})^2 \quad (\text{eq. 4})$$

3.2. Effect of eugenyl acetate content on thermal properties of plasticized PLA.

The efficiency of a plasticizer can be assessed by its ability to depress the glass transition temperature, T_g , of the base polymer [68, 69]. **Figure 2** gathers the variation of the main thermal transitions of neat PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with increasing EAc loading (see Supplementary Information for DSC traces, and main thermal results corresponding to 1st heating cycle: **Figure SI.1** and **Table SI.2**; cooling cycle: **Figure SI.2** and **Table SI.3**; and 2nd heating cycle: **Figure SI.3** and **Table SI.4**). As it can be seen in **Figure 2a**, the T_g of neat PLA, located at $60.4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, decreases almost linearly as the EAc loading increases, and these values are consistent with those predicted by the Fox equation for miscible systems (**Equation 5**), and a most general expression that takes into account polymer-plasticizer interactions, as proposed by Gordon-Taylor (**Equation 6**). See Supporting Information, **Figure SI.3** with DSC traces corresponding to the 2nd heating cycle, and **Table SI.4** with the characteristic temperatures and enthalpies related to the main thermal transitions. As it can be seen, the degree of crystallinity of PLA and its plasticized formulations with EAc is very low, ranging from 3.3% for neat PLA to values in the 4.0 – 4.3% in plasticized PLA with EAc in the 5 – 15 wt.% range. The highest crystallinity is observed for the plasticized formulation with 20 wt.% EAc

with a value of 9.1%. These results are in accordance with XRD patterns in Figure SI.4, where a mainly amorphous structure can be seen for all formulations, except that with 20 wt.% EAc which shows a well-defined peak at $2\theta=16.6^\circ$ corresponding to the (110) plane of the α -crystal form of PLA.

$$\frac{1}{T_g} = \frac{w_1}{T_{g1}} + \frac{w_2}{T_{g2}} \quad (\text{eq. 5})$$

$$T_g = \frac{w_1 T_{g1} + k w_2 T_{g2}}{w_1 + k w_2} \quad (\text{eq. 6})$$

where T_g stands for the glass transition of the plasticized PLA, w_1 , and w_2 , represent the weight fraction of PLA and EAc, respectively, while T_{g1} , and T_{g2} are the glass transition temperatures of PLA and EAc. Finally, k in the Gordon-Taylor equation is related to the interaction between PLA and EAc. T_{g2} has been estimated by the group contribution method proposed by Camacho-Zuñiga *et al.* [70], following **Equation 7**.

$$T_{g2} = \frac{1}{M} \sum (T_g M)_i \quad (\text{eq. 7})$$

where T_{g2} and M represent the glass transition temperature and the molecular weight of eugenyl acetate, and the term $(T_g M)_i$ stands for the different group contributions to T_g . By considering the chemical structure of EAc, its glass transition temperature can be assumed to be -40.9°C . As can be seen in **Figure 2a**, the experimental values obtained for plasticized PLA with different EAc loading, are in accordance with those predicted by the Fox equation, and the Gordon-Taylor equation with an optimized k parameter of 1.42

which gives almost the same results predicted by the Fox equation. In fact, the Gordon-Taylor equation becomes the Fox equation for a k value of $T_{g1}/T_{g2} = 1.44$.

Figure 2. Plot evolution of a) the glass transition temperature, T_g ; b) the cold crystallization peak temperature, T_{cc} ; and c) the melt peak temperature, T_m , as a function of increasing EAc loading in plasticized PLA formulations.

The lowest value of T_g is obtained for the plasticized formulation containing 20 wt.% EAc and is 35.7 °C, which represents a depression of almost 25 °C in T_g , thus corroborating the exceptional plasticization efficiency of EAc. As reported by Blázquez-Blázquez *et al.* [71], plasticizers such as acetyl tri-n-butyl citrate (ATBC), or trioctyl trimellitates (TOTM), contribute to improve ductility and processing of PLA by reducing the intensity of the intra- and intermolecular interactions within the polymer chains thus allowing enhanced chain mobility, which in turn, leads to a depression of T_g . At a concentration of 18 wt.%, both plasticizers provided a depression of T_g from around 60 °C to 27 °C, similar to that observed in this study. Similar behaviour has been reported by Maiza *et al.* [30], in PLA plasticized with citrate esters. In addition, plasticizers contribute to increase the free volume, having a positive effect on improved chain mobility [72, 73]. Eugenyl acetate also exerts a noticeable effect on the cold crystallization peak of PLA. As the chain mobility increases due to reduction on T_g , the cold crystallization moves towards lower temperatures as can be seen in **Figure SI.1**, and **Figure SI.3** (Supplementary Information), corresponding to the 1st, and 2nd DSC traces of the heating cycles, respectively. The characteristic peak maximum of the cold crystallization decreases almost linearly with increasing EAc loading as seen in **Figure 2b**. This phenomenon is directly related to improved chain mobility due to free volume increase and the weakening the intra- and intermolecular attraction forces, which provides an internal lubrication effect on polymer chains, as described by the lubricant theory of plasticization [74-76]. This phenomenon is responsible for the shift of the cold crystallization to lower temperatures. Notably, the cold crystallization peak (T_{cc}) changes from 105.8 °C for neat PLA down to such low values of 86.2 °C for the plasticized formulations with 20 wt.% EAc. Despite the Fox and Gordon-Taylor equations were not developed to predict the shift in the cold crystallization, as the decrease in T_{cc} is directly

related with T_g depression, both equations give good fitting too, as expected (**Figure 2b**). The crystallization temperature of EAc used for the model fitting, has been 28.0 °C as reported in literature [77]. In the case of the Gordon-Taylor equation, the best fit is obtained for a k value of 1.44 which is close to the k value of 1.26 which converts the Gordon-Taylor equation to the Fox equation. As can be seen in **Figure SI1** and **Figure SI.3** (Supplementary Information), neat PLA shows an exothermic pre-melting crystallization peak at 158.5 °C which is related to the transition of α' crystals to α form [78, 79]. This pre-melting peak is not observed in all plasticized formulations, showing a unique endothermic melting peak which is also shifted to lower temperatures with increasing EAc loading. Anyway, this decrease is less pronounced than that observed for the shift in T_g and T_{cc} , as seen in **Figure 2c**. Maiza *et al.* [30], have concluded that an efficient plasticizer not only promotes a decrease in T_g of the amorphous domains, but also on the melting process of the crystalline regions, as demonstrated by Greco *et al.* [80], in plasticized PLA with cardanol-derived plasticizers. This phenomenon is predicted by the Flory-Huggins equation (**Equation 8**), that allows correlating the melt temperature of a neat polymer and a polymer blend [66, 81].

$$\frac{1}{T_{mp}} - \frac{1}{T_m^0} = \frac{R}{\Delta H} \frac{v_u}{v_1} (\phi_1 - \chi\phi_1^2) \quad (\text{eq. 8})$$

Where T_{mp} stands for the predicted melt peak temperature of the plasticized PLA with ϕ_1 volume fraction of EAc; T_m^0 is the melt peak temperature of the neat polymer, PLA; R is the universal gas constant (8.314 J/mol K); ΔH represents the melt enthalpy of neat polymer and is 93.7 J/g \approx 6746.4 J/mol for PLA; v_u , and v_1 stand for the molar volume of the neat polymer (PLA), and the plasticizer (EAc), respectively. χ stands for

the Flory-Huggins polymer-solvent (in this case, the plasticizer). As seen in **Figure 2c**, the experimental values of the melt peak temperature of PLA agree with those predicted by the Flory-Huggins theory.

Despite low molecular weight monomeric plasticizers provide exceptional ductile properties to PLA, one drawback is their volatility compared to oligomeric or polymeric plasticizers. Moreover, low molecular weight plasticizers have more tendency to migrate [74], which could limit their use in food contact applications. Due to their volatility, some plasticizer could be lost during processing as observed in plasticized PLA with terpenes [64, 82], maleates, and fumarates [83]. Anyway, even with this plasticizer loss, the ductile properties are notably improved with these compounds. Thermogravimetry (TGA) is very useful to assess the plasticizer loss during processing. As can be seen in **Figure 3**, neat PLA has no significant weight loss until the onset degradation temperature is reached (T_5), located at 339.1 °C. As the EAc content increases, the characteristic TGA curves show two separate weight loss steps. A first one, comprised between 200 – 300 °C which is attributed to plasticizer volatilization, and a second weight loss in the 325 – 375 °C which corresponds to PLA degradation. These two clearly weight loss steps have also been reported by Barandiaran *et al.* [31], in plasticized PLA with cinnamates. As can be seen in **Table 1**, the onset degradation temperature (T_5) decreases as the EAc loading increases, with minimum values of 204.4 °C, and 206.5 °C for 15 wt.% and 20 wt.% EAc content. This temperature is above the typical processing conditions of PLA at 190 °C. This confirms very low plasticizer loss during processing as seen in **Table 1**. Regarding the formulations with 20 wt.% EAc, it is worthy to note that the remaining weigh at 200 °C is 95.3 wt.% which means low plasticizer removal during processing as seen for the other formulations. At 325 °C, the remaining weight for this same formulation is 81.2 °C, close to theoretical PLA wt.% (80 wt.%). The decrease in the onset degradation

temperature has been observed by Brdlík *et al.* [84], in plasticized PLA with polyethyleneglycol (PEG), with a decrease from 313.4 °C (neat PLA), to 259.4 °C with 15 wt.% PEG (400 g/mol). Maiza *et al.* [85], have also found similar results in plasticized PLA with triethyl citrate (TEC), and acetyltributyl citrate (ATBC). They reported a T_5 for neat PLA of 348.94 °C, which decreased to 211.04 °C, and 254.00 °C for plasticized formulations containing 20 wt.% TEC, and ATBC, respectively. Therefore, the results obtained with EAc, are similar to that of the widely used TEC as biobased plasticizer for PLA. Regarding the maximum degradation temperature rate (T_{max}), as it is related to the thermal degradation of remaining PLA above 325 °C, it remains almost constant at about 363 – 364 °C which is consistent with the values reported by Abdelwahab *et al.* [86], that observed a T_{max} of 357 °C, and almost the same value for PLA formulations with Lapol(R) 108 bioplasticizer, and binary blends with PHB. In a similar way, the endset of the thermal decomposition of PLA and plasticized PLA (T_{95}), remains constant (around 379 °C) since it refers to the PLA weight fraction of the plasticized samples with EAc.

Figure 3. Thermal degradation profiles obtained by thermogravimetry (TGA) of PLA and plasticized PLA with varying eugenyl acetate (EAc) content, a) mass loss, and b) first derivative (DTG).

Table 1. Main thermal parameters of PLA and plasticized PLA with varying eugenyl acetate (EAc) content, obtained thermogravimetry (TGA).

Code	Nominal wt.% EAc	Remaining wt.% at 200 °C	Remaining wt.% at 325 °C	T ₅ (°C)	T _{max} (°C)	T ₉₅ (°C)
PLA	0	99.9	98.9	339.1	362.5	379.2
PLA/5EAc	5	98.4	90.0	293.9	364.8	378.6
PLA/10EAc	10	97.7	91.5	243.9	364.4	379.2
PLA/15EAc	15	96.3	84.5	204.4	363.7	379.6
PLA/20EAc	20	95.3	81.2	206.5	364.3	380.4

3.3. Mechanical properties of PLA plasticized with eugenyl acetate.

Figure 4 gathers the main mechanical properties of plasticized formulations containing different EAc loading. As expected, neat PLA is a rather brittle polymer with very small strain at break (ϵ_B) of 10.2%, and a relatively high stress at break (σ_B) of 71.1 MPa, similar to common values reported in literature, with ϵ_B varying between 3.0 - 10.0%, and σ_B comprised in the 55 – 70 MPa range, depending on the commercial grade and/or processing technique and conditions [87, 88]. As Llanes *et al.* [83], have reported, it is necessary the plasticizer content reaches a percolation threshold to provide effective plasticization effects. If the plasticizer content is lower than this threshold, it occupies the free volume inside the polymer matrix and the overall effects on ductile properties are not observed. This phenomenon is known as antiplasticization [65, 89], and is responsible for even lower ϵ_B values in plasticized PLA formulations below this threshold. This is attributed to the disturbance created by the plasticizer molecules inside the PLA matrix at low concentrations, with a reduction of the free volume of PLA polymer chains [90].

Figure 4. Mechanical properties of neat PLA and plasticized PLA as a function of increasing EAc content: a) stress at break, σ_B ; b) strain at break, ϵ_B ; c) ultimate tensile toughness, U_T ; d) impact strength, $a_{cN}+23$; e) stress (σ) – strain (ϵ) tensile curves; f) Shore D hardness.

This phenomenon is observed in this work with low EAc content of 5 wt.%, and 10 wt.% with ϵ_B values of 7.8%, and 7.4%, respectively. At a concentration of 15 wt.% EAc, the plasticization effects are clearly seen, with an exceptional ϵ_B of 265.5%, which means the threshold for the antiplasticization-to-plasticization mechanisms is located between 10 – 15 wt.% EAc. As it has been reported in literature, this threshold is usually in the 10 – 20 wt.% range [65, 91], which is consistent with the obtained results. At a concentration of 20 wt.% EAc, the ϵ_B dramatically increases up to 427.7%, corroborating the exceptional plasticization effect predicted by the noticeable decrease in T_g observed by DSC. As can be seen in **Figure 4a**, the stress at break, σ_B , decreases from 71.1 MPa (neat PLA), to values around 20 MPa, which are typical of some polyethylene commercial grades with similar ϵ_B values.

This confirms plasticized PLA with EAc is a sound environmentally friendly candidate to substitute some commodity plastics. The antiplasticization phenomenon can also be seen by comparing the ultimate tensile toughness (U_T) (**Figure 4c**), measured as the area under stress (σ) – strain (ϵ) tensile curves in **Figure 4e**. U_T changes from 4.1 MJ/m³ for neat PLA, consistent with literature reports [92-95], to even lower values for plasticized PLA formulations with 5, and 10 wt.% EAc, while a notable increase up to 32.3 MJ/m³, and 43.0 MJ/m³ for formulations with 15, and 20 wt.% EAc. These results are comparable to those reported by Zych *et al.* [96], in plasticized PLA with 40 wt.% epoxidized soybean oil methyl ester (ESOME). The improved toughness was also confirmed by Charpy impact tests with notched samples (**Figure 4d**). The impact strength for neat PLA is 3.4 kJ/m². According to the antiplasticization phenomenon observed in tensile tests for low (5 – 10 wt.%) EAc, the impact strength also decreases for these formulations. Nevertheless, once the threshold has reached, the impact strength increases to 5.0 kJ/m² and, surprisingly, the formulation with 20 wt.% EAc does not break. Similar

results have been described by Ivorra-Martinez *et al.* [97], in plasticized PLA with dibutyl itaconate (DBI) at a concentration of 15 and 20 wt.% DBI. Ma *et al.* [98], have also observed this noticeable increase in the impact strength in plasticized PLA with furan-based elastomers. Murariu *et al.* [65], also observed the antiplasticization effect on toughness of PLA plasticized with acetyltributyl citrate (ATBC), glyceryl triacetate (GTA), and dioctyl adipate (DOA), and exceptional impact strength values 11-fold higher than neat PLA with 20 wt.% DOA. Regarding the Shore D hardness, it follows the same evolution of σ_B , with noticeable changes in compositions containing 15, and 20 wt.% EAc (**Figure 4f**).

Characterization of the surface morphology of fractured specimens after impact test, gives support to the obtained mechanical properties. **Figure 5** shows the FESEM images of neat PLA and its plasticized formulations with different EAc loading. PLA has a brittle behaviour as confirmed by the low impact strength and elongation or strain at break. This means almost no plastic deformation occurs during the impact test. The morphology of fractured PLA shows typical flat low roughness surfaces (**Figure 5b**). This fracture is characteristic of brittle polymers with no (or very small) plastic deformation. In fact, this fracture morphology has also been confirmed in cryofractured PLA specimens to avoid plastic deformation [99]. As EAc content increases, clear evidence of plastic deformation can be seen. In plasticized PLA formulations with 5 wt.% EAc, the surface roughness increases (**Figure 5c**). Moreover, wavy or twisted regions, with presence of more microcracks and filaments can be seen at higher magnification (2000 \times) (**Figure 5d**). Despite these signs of plastic deformation, these materials appear to be brittle as per the low strain at break and low impact toughness. Similar morphologies have been reported in literature in PLA with low plasticizer content [91, 97].

Figure 5. FESEM images at a magnification of 500 \times , (left column) and 2000 \times (right column), corresponding to the fractured specimens from impact tests of PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with varying eugenyl acetate content, a)-b) PLA, c)-d) PLA/5EAc, e)-f) PLA/10EAc, g)-h) PLA/15EAc, and i)-j) PLA/20EAc.

This behaviour can be seen for plasticized PLA formulations containing 10 wt.% EAc. Nevertheless, for plasticized formulations with 15 wt.% EAc, the surface morphology shows increased roughness, as well as more wavy/twisted regions which are representative of plastic deformation (**Figure 5g** and **5h**). The presence of wavy/twisted regions is more pronounced in plasticized PLA with 20 wt.% EAc as seen in **Figure 5j** at 2000 \times , which showed the highest strain at break of all the formulations developed in this work. Similar twisted regions have been observed by Gomez-Caturla *et al.* [91], in plasticized PLA with 20 – 30 wt.% tartrate-based plasticizers, achieving elongation at break values comprised between 460 – 570 %.

3.4. Thermomechanical properties of PLA plasticized with eugenyl acetate.

Dynamic-mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) is a powerful tool to assess the effects of temperature and dynamic loads on mechanical properties of polymers. Moreover, it provides valuable information about polymer chain motions, and therefore, information about thermal transitions. **Figure 6** gathers the plots of the storage modulus (E'), the loss modulus (E''), and the dynamic damping factor ($\tan \delta$), with increasing temperature for neat PLA and its plasticized formulations with increasing EAc loading. **Table 2** summarizes the main thermal parameters obtained by DMTA analysis. Regarding the evolution of storage modulus, E' with temperature (**Figure 6a**), neat PLA shows two clear thermal transitions. Below 50 °C, E' is almost constant (glassy state), showing thermomechanical stability [75]. A pronounced decrease (of about three orders of magnitude) can be observed above 55 °C, which is attributed to the glass transition. The cold crystallization can be seen as an increase in E' above 80 °C, thus confirming the previous results obtained by DSC. As the EAc loading increases, the E' vs T curves are shifted to lower temperature ranges due to increased chain mobility [73]. Therefore, both

the glass transition, and the cold crystallization processes are moved to lower temperatures. These phenomena can also be seen by the evolution of the loss modulus, E'' with temperature (**Figure 6b**). The peak between 50 – 70 °C stands for the glass transition region, while the cold crystallization is associated to the increase in E'' above 80 °C. The appearance of a single peak in $\tan \delta$ vs temperature, is also indicative of a unique T_g which confirms no phase separation occurs [69]. By considering the peak maximum criteria T_g values have been calculated and gathered in **Table 2** (see Supplementary Information, **Table SI.5** for characteristic temperatures of both glass transition, and cold crystallization following different criteria related to E' , E'' , and $\tan \delta$). Neat PLA possesses a T_g of 64.3 °C, while this decreases almost linearly with increasing EAc loading down to such values of 27.2 °C for the plasticized formulation with 20 wt.% EAc. These results confirm the exceptional plasticization properties EAc can provide to PLA. The above mentioned antiplasticization phenomenon can also be seen by DMTA, by comparing the E' values at room temperature (see **Table 2**). Neat PLA shows an E' value of 2041 MPa, typical of a brittle polymer. For low EAc concentrations (5, and 10 wt.%), the E' does not change in a significant way, thus confirming the brittleness of these formulations. Nevertheless, the formulation with 15 wt.% EAc shows an E' value of 1347 MPa which confirms the threshold to activate the flexibility mechanisms has been triggered. As expected, the formulation with 20 wt.% shows the lowest E' in this study, with a value of 587 MPa, which agrees with the previous mechanical properties obtained by tensile tests. Ma *et al.* [98], have observed this same behaviour, but less pronounced, in plasticized PLA with increasing furan-based elastomer as plasticizer, with a change in E' from ~3000 MPa (neat PLA), down to ~2100 MPa for the plasticized formulation with 25% furan-based elastomer.

Figure 6. Dynamic-mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) of PLA and flexible PLA formulations with varying eugenyl acetate content, with increasing temperature: a) storage modulus – E' , b) loss modulus – E'' , and c) dynamic damping factor – $\tan \delta$.

Table 2. Thermal and dynamic-mechanical properties of PLA and flexible PLA formulations with varying eugenyl acetate content, with increasing temperature obtained by dynamic-mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA).

Code	E' (MPa) at 25 °C	T _g * (°C)	T _{cc_onset} ** (°C)
PLA	2041	64.3	76.5
PLA/5EAc	2038	55.2	70.1
PLA/10EAc	2046	49.2	64.7
PLA/15EAc	1347	38.9	59.1
PLA/20EAc	587	34.3	58.5

* The T_g has been obtained using the peak maximum of tan δ .

** The T_{cc_onset} has been obtained as the onset of the E' vs T increase after the glass transition region.

In addition to DMTA and DSC analysis, thermomechanical analysis (TMA) gives interesting insights on thermal transitions observed by these techniques. As it is depicted in **Figure 7**, the effect of increasing EAc content on dimensional change of plasticized PLA formulations with temperature can be seen. Regarding PLA (and all its plasticized formulations), its TMA plot shows three different regions. Below 48.3 °C, we see a linear correlation between dimensional change and temperature. In this region, the material behaves as a glassy material and its characteristic coefficient of linear thermal expansion (CLTE) can be calculated as shown in **Table 3**, with a value of 30.8 $\mu\text{m}/(\text{m } ^\circ\text{C})$ for neat PLA. Espinach *et al.* [100], have reported values of 79.3 $\mu\text{m}/(\text{m } ^\circ\text{C})$ for neat PLA in the 35 – 50 °C range, which is consistent with the results obtained in this work. They also noted a discontinuity of the linear correlation in the 60 – 100 °C which was attributed to the softening of the material due to the glass transition. As seen in **Figure 7**, this same

discontinuity in neat PLA and its plasticized formulations with EAc can be clearly observed. In the case of PLA, the temperature range for this discontinuity comprises the temperature range from 48.3 °C to 85.4 °C. Above 85.4 °C, a new linear correlation of dimensional change with temperature can be seen, which corresponds to a region above T_g with a rubber-like behaviour. This can be confirmed by the increase in CLTE to 63.0 $\mu\text{m}/(\text{m } ^\circ\text{C})$ for neat PLA. Same behaviour can be observed for all other compositions with a shift of the characteristic T_g onset, and T_g endset to lower temperatures as observed by DMTA and DSC. The plasticization effect can also be observed by an increase in the CLTE with increasing EAc loading (**Table 3**). In some cases, this discontinuity region is attributed to the overlapping of two thermal phenomena that counteracts, namely the glass transition, and the cold crystallization [32, 94]. In general, the glass transition leads to increased dimensional change (expansion), while the cold crystallization provides a more packed structure which in turn, leads to contraction, thus counteracting the effect of the softening. As can be seen in **Figure 7**, the most relevant effect observed in neat PLA and in all its plasticized formulations with EAc is a clear expansion, thus indicating the prevalence of the glass transition in this temperature range.

Figure 7. Dimensional change of PLA and flexible PLA formulations with varying eugenyl acetate content, with increasing temperature, obtained by thermomechanical analysis (TMA).

Table 3. Thermal properties of PLA and flexible PLA formulations with varying eugenyl acetate content, with increasing temperature obtained by thermomechanical analysis (TMA).

Code	CLTE below T_g	T_g onset ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_g endset ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	CLTE above T_g
	$[\mu\text{m}/(\text{m } ^{\circ}\text{C})]$			$[\mu\text{m}/(\text{m } ^{\circ}\text{C})]$
PLA	30.8	48.3	85.4	63.0
PLA/5EAc	31.0	42.3	78.3	63.5
PLA/10EAc	34.7	39.4	73.5	63.7
PLA/15EAc	46.6	36.8	64.2	89.4
PLA/20EAc	40.0	35.4	54.6	110.1

3.4. Disintegration in controlled compost soil of PLA plasticized with eugenyl acetate.

The evaluation of the disintegration rate in controlled compost soil is necessary to assess the low environmental impact of the plasticized PLA formulations containing different EAc loading. **Figure 8** shows the visual aspect of the different formulations as a function of the composting time in weeks. It is worthy to note all the formulations are initially transparent (week 0), and clear signs of degradation such as loss of transparency, presence of cracks and, obviously, mass loss can be seen as the composting time increases. These phenomena have also been observed by Ramos *et al.* [101], in functional PLA films containing silver nanoparticles and thymol. Nevertheless, as they developed thin films, the disintegration time was remarkably lower of 14 days. Similar findings were reported by Garcia-Garcia *et al.* [102], in plasticized PLA with epoxidized karanja oil at different concentrations. All the formulations they developed were fully disintegrated in less than 20 days since they also worked with thin films. Nevertheless, Gomez-Caturra *et al.* [91], reported disintegration times of about 49 days in injection molded specimens of PLA and tartrate-based plasticizers. They also observed the plasticizer content also promotes disintegration to occur faster due to plasticizer molecules have low molecular weight. Moreover, the ester groups of tartrate are easily hydrolyzed during composting, thus favouring disintegration. As can be seen in **Figure 9**, all the plasticized PLA formulations with EAc are fully disintegrated in approximately 6-8 weeks (<90% weight loss). As plasticizers increase the free volume of the base polymer, they make easier water to enter into the bulk polymer and promote hydrolyzation of the ester groups to give oligomers and monomers [103]. (see Supplementary Information, **Figure SI.5** with the results of the water uptake with time which shows the plasticizer increases the water uptake due to an increase in the free volume). This phenomenon promotes the decrease in the molecular weight, and subsequently, and increase in crystallinity which leads to the characteristic

transparency loss. Then, microcracks appear and they promote fracture and as the time goes by, the polymer is progressively disintegrated.

Figure 8. Visual appearance of PLA and PLA specimens plasticized with varying eugenyl acetate content, during the disintegration in controlled compost soil test.

Figure 9. Mass loss evolution as a function of the incubation time corresponding to PLA and PLA formulations with varying eugenyl acetate content.

4. Conclusions.

We have demonstrated the feasibility of using eugenyl acetate (EAc), as a biobased and widely available plasticizer for industrial polylactide-PLA formulations with improved ductility. The intrinsic chemical structure of eugenyl acetate, with an ester group, an aromatic ring, and a short hydrocarbon side chain, are key features to provide good miscibility and plasticization to PLA as corroborated by similar solubility Hansen solubility parameters of $20.66 \text{ MPa}^{1/2}$ (PLA), and $19.83 \text{ MPa}^{1/2}$ (EAc). This good miscibility was also confirmed by calculating the interaction parameter (χ) of the Flory-Huggins lattice theory with a value of 0.39 which confirmed exceptional miscibility and no phase separation. PLA is a brittle polymer with a strain at break of 10.2%, and the addition of low EAc concentrations of 5 – 10 wt.%, do not provide increased toughness, but a decrease in stress at break can be observed. At an EAc content of 15 wt.% or above,

the plasticization effects are exceptional, with an increase in strain at break up to 427.7% (20 wt.% EAc). This exceptional plasticization effect was also confirmed by a noticeable depression in the glass transition temperature (T_g) of neat PLA (60.4 °C) down to 35.7 °C with 20 wt.% EAc. As predicted by the Flory-Huggins theory, the melt peak temperature was shifted to lower values with increasing EAc loading. Field emission scanning electron microscopy revealed good miscibility of EAc in the PLA matrix, and clear evidence of plastic deformation (twisted and wavy regions) were observed in plasticized formulations with 15 – 20 wt.% EAc. All the developed formulations were fully disintegrated in controlled compost soil conditions thus showing the feasibility of these formulations as environmentally friendly solutions that positively contribute to sustainable development. Moreover, despite eugenyl acetate is a naturally occurring compound present in cloves, cinnamon, pepper, oregano, among others, it is also a model compound that can be obtained from lignin fragmentation, thus widening the potential of lignin as raw material for the development of biobased chemicals for the polymer industry.

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Author contributions.

D. Barrera-Juca: Investigation, Data curation, Validation, Writing original draft, Visualization; **R. Balart:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Project administration, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition; **C. Lazaro-Hdez:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Validation, Data curation; **J. Gomez-Caturla:** Resources, Methodology, Visualization, Project administration; **N. Guijarro:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition; **X. Marset:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

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